

Studies on Some Polydentate Ligands. I

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Synthesis and characterisation of two new hexadentate ligands, 1,2-bis(o-1-methyltriazene-1-oxido-3-phenylthio)ethane and 1,2-bis(o-1-ethyltriazene-1-oxido-3-phenylthio)ethane and their chelates with some bivalent transition metal ions are described.

WE recently synthesised¹ two new hexadentate ligands, 1,2-bis(o-1-methyltriazene-1-oxido-3-phenoxy)ethane (DMTPE) and 1,2-bis(o-1-ethyltriazene-1-oxido-3-phenoxy)ethane (DETPTE), and their metal chelates with Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II). In this communication we report the synthesis and chelating properties of the sulfur analogues of these ligands i.e., 1,2-bis(o-1-methyltriazene-1-oxido-3-phenylthio)ethane (DMTPTE), (Ia) and 1,2-bis(o-1-ethyltriazene-1-oxido-3-phenylthio)ethane (DETPTE), (Ib).

These two ligands act as hexadentate ligands utilising the two sulfur atoms, the two nitrogen atoms linked to the benzene ring and the two oxygen atoms, so that six-coordinate metal chelates of the type M(ligand-2H) are obtained with all the four metal ions, Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II).

The synthesis of the present ligands (I) has been achieved by introduction of triazene-1-oxido group in place of the amino group in the ligand (II).

The synthesis of the above quadridentate ligand (II) was reported by Unger² as early as in 1897. Dwyer³ *et al* in 1967 studied the chelating properties of these ligands.

Experimental

Preparation of ligands: The two ligands were synthesised by coupling the appropriate diazonium salts and substituted hydroxylamine in an acetate buffer at 0°. Details of preparations are as follows.

1, 2-bis(o-1-methyltriazene-1-oxido-3-phenylthio)ethane (DMTPTE): 1.75 g of 1,2-bis(o-aminophenylthio)ethane (II) was taken in 50% hydrochloric acid (4 ml HCl, 4 ml H₂O) and diazotised by 1.15 g of sodium nitrite in 2 ml water. The temperature of the solution was maintained between 0-5°. This diazonium salt solution was added with stirring to 1.12 g of N-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride in 50 ml of water, cooled to 0°. The pH of the reaction mixture was kept in the range 3-5 by slow and simultaneous addition of 7 g of sodium acetate in 20 ml of water. The solution was stirred for 10 more min. After the addition of diazonium salt solution was completed, a pale yellow precipitate separated out. This was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol to yield pale yellow needles. Analysis: C, 48.82; H, 5.42; N, 21.72; S, 16.01. C₁₆S₂H₂₀N₆O₂ requires C, 48.97; H, 5.14; N, 21.42; S, 16.34%; m.p. 169-70°.

1, 2-bis(o-1-ethyltriazene-1-oxido-3-phenylthio)ethane (DETPTE): The same procedure was used for the preparation of the DETPTE using N-ethylhydroxylamine hydrochloride as coupling agent. Analysis: C, 51.18; H, 5.63; N, 19.80; S, 15.72. C₁₈S₂H₂₄N₆O₂ requires C, 51.14; H, 5.75; N, 19.99; S, 15.25%; m.p. 171-73°.

Preparation of the complexes:

Manganese(II) complexes: A solution of manganese acetate (1.2 g; 0.005 M) was added to ethanolic solution of ligand (2.0 g of DMTPTE or 2.1 g of DETPTE; 0.005 M). The contents were refluxed for about half an hour and crystalline complexes separated out on concentration. The complexes were washed with hot water and finally with alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over P₄O₁₀. They are insoluble in water and ethanol but soluble in acetone and chloroform.

Cobalt(II) complexes: Aqueous solution of cobalt acetate (1.3 g; 0.005 M) prepared in minimum volume of water was added to ethanolic solution of ligand (2.0 g of DMTPTE or 2.1 g of DETPTE; 0.005 M). The contents were refluxed for about half an hour and red crystalline complexes separated out on concentration. The complexes were washed with hot water and finally with alcohol and dried in

a vacuum desiccator over P_4O_{10} . They are insoluble in water and ethanol but soluble in acetone and chloroform.

Copper(II) complexes: Alcoholic solution of copper(II) acetate (1.0 g; 0.005 M) was added to ethanolic solution of ligand (2.0 g of DMTPTE or 2.1 g of DETPTE; 0.005 M). The contents were refluxed for about half an hour and on concentration, pale red crystalline complexes separated out. The complexes were washed with hot water and finally with alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over P_4O_{10} . These complexes are insoluble in water and ethanol but soluble in acetone and chloroform.

Nickel(II) complexes: Aqueous solution of nickel chloride (1.2 g; 0.005 M) was added to ethanolic solution of ligand (2.0 g DMTPTE or 2.1 g DETPTE; 0.005 M). The contents were refluxed for about half an hour and on concentration, green crystalline complexes separated out. The complexes were washed with hot water and finally with alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over P_4O_{10} . Both the complexes are insoluble in water and ethanol but soluble in acetone and chloroform.

Physical measurements: NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer. Tetramethylsilane was used as the internal standard and frequencies were measured by the side band technique.

Infrared spectra were taken in KBr pellets or in chloroform solutions on a Perkin Elmer 621 spectrophotometer.

The magnetic susceptibilities were measured on a Gouy balance, using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as calibrant ($\chi_g = 16.46 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs). The diamagnetic corrections for the ligand atoms and cations were computed using Pascal's constants¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

Structure of the ligands: The two tautomeric forms (IIIa) or (IIIb) are possible for the ligands under discussion. NMR spectra of the two ligands

(DMTPTE and DETPTE) in $CDCl_3$ have a low field signal (-1.4 and -1.5 τ), which is of the correct intensity to represent the N-H protons and confirms the existence of the molecule in (IIIb) form. If the ligands exist in (IIIa) form, there must be a singlet for O-H. This is usually located²⁷ at very low field ($\sim -5\tau$) while N-H proton is very often found around -3 τ . The lowering in the position may be attributed to hydrogen bonding. But no O-H singlet is present in the spectra. So the structure of the ligands can be confirmed as (IIIb) and not as (IIIa).

This examination leads us to conclude that the corresponding compounds having $R=CH_3$ or C_2H_5 are correctly formulated as 1,2-bis(o-1-alkyltriazeno-1-oxido-3-phenylthio)ethane (type IIIb).

Some representative nmr data for the ligands are shown in Table 1. The spectrum of DMTPTE, taken in $CDCl_3$, gives rise to a singlet at 5.95 τ representing the two methyl groups. The ethylene group ($-CH_2-CH_2-$) is found to give a singlet at 7.08 τ .

TABLE 1—PROTON RESONANCE FREQUENCIES OF THE LIGANDS IN $CDCl_3$

Ligands	Group	Chemical shifts ppm (τ)
DMTPTE	NCH_3	5.95
	$-CH_2-CH_2-$	7.08
	$-C_6H_5$ (aromatic protons)	2.40–3.10
DETPTE	NH	-1.40
	NCH_2CH_3 (due to CH_3 group)	8.45 (t, $J=7.5$ Hz)
	NCH_2CH_3 (due to CH_2 group)	5.80 (q, $J=7.5$ Hz)
	$-C_6H_5$ (aromatic protons)	2.30–2.55
	NH	-1.50
	$-CH_2-CH_2-$	7.05

The aromatic protons (in two benzene rings) appear as multiplets in the region 2.40 to 3.10 τ . The intensity ratio of the ethylene group and two methyl groups is 1.50.

Similarly, the nmr spectrum of DETPTE in $CDCl_3$ has a low field signal (-1.50 τ), which is assignable to the N-H protons. This compound gives rise to one singlet at 7.05 τ representing the ethylene group ($-CH_2-CH_2-$). The two methylene groups of C_2H_5 give one quartet in the region 5.50–5.90 τ ($J=7.5$ Hz). These signals are assigned to $-N-CH_2-$ on the basis of their chemical shifts at higher field. The two methyl groups of C_2H_5 give one triplet in the region 8.30–8.56 τ ($J=7.5$ Hz). The aromatic protons in the two benzene rings give one multiplet in the region 2.30–2.55 τ .

Structure of the complexes: All the complexes have 1 : 1 metal : ligand composition. The triazene-1-oxide group is known to act as bidentate. The coordination ability of the thioetheral sulfurs of the ligands is also well established⁴⁻⁹. The two ligands may, therefore, act as binate hexadentate ligands forming neutral six-coordinate complexes (IV).

(IV)
M(II) = Mn(II), Co(II), Cu(II) or Ni(II) and
R = $-CH_3$, $-C_2H_5$

The room temperature magnetic moment values (Table 2) for all the complexes are in conformity with such a structure in copper(II), nickel(II) and manganese(II). Complexes show normal magnetic

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF THE Mn(II), Co(II), Cu(II) AND Ni(II) CHELATES

	Colour	% C Found (Calcd.)	% H Found (Calcd.)	% N Found (Calcd.)	% S Found (Calcd.)	%M Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
Mn(DMTPTE-2H)	Red	43.40 (43.14)	3.99 (4.07)	18.95 (18.87)	14.61 (14.39)	12.05 (12.35)	6.02 4.50
Co(DMTPTE-2H)	Red	42.99 (42.76)	4.06 (4.04)	18.57 (18.70)	14.02 (14.26)	13.40 (13.11)	1.84
Cu(DMTPTE-2H)	Brown	42.10 (42.32)	3.97 (3.99)	18.32 (18.51)	14.43 (14.13)	13.79 (13.99)	3.22
Ni(DMTPTE-2H)	Green	42.53 (42.78)	4.07 (4.04)	18.90 (18.71)	14.45 (14.27)	12.85 (13.07)	6.11
Mn(DETPTE-2H)	Red	45.25 (45.66)	4.62 (4.68)	17.51 (17.75)	13.69 (13.54)	11.28 (11.60)	4.39
Co(DETPTE-2H)	Brown	45.60 (45.28)	4.81 (4.64)	17.41 (17.60)	13.75 (13.43)	12.03 (12.34)	1.99
Cu(DETPTE-2H)	Brown	44.62 (44.84)	4.57 (4.60)	17.29 (17.43)	13.08 (13.30)	13.41 (13.18)	3.11
Ni(DETPTE-2H)	Green	45.02 (45.29)	4.56 (4.65)	17.85 (17.61)	13.59 (13.43)	12.61 (12.30)	

moments corresponding to one, two and five unpaired spins, associated with expected orbital contributions.

In an octahedral crystal field, the magnetic moment¹¹⁻²⁰ for high-spin cobalt(II) (S=3/2) is expected to be 5.2 B.M. at 300 K. Low spin cobalt(II) complexes possess the electronic configuration $t_{2g}^6 e_g^1$. The magnetic moment is expected²¹⁻²³ to be temperature independent and fairly close to 1.9 B.M. However, cobalt(II) complexes can show magnetic moment at room temperature which is in between for the two spin-states and such intermediate values can arise due to any of the following mechanisms :

- (i) partial oxidation of cobalt(II) to cobalt(III),
- (ii) antiferromagnetic exchange interactions,
- (iii) equilibrium between the thermally accessible 2E_g and $^4T_{2g}$ states i.e., $^4T_{2g} \rightleftharpoons ^2E_g$

The lowering in the magnetic moment in the cobalt(II) complexes under study as a result of partial oxidation of cobalt(II) to cobalt(III) is ruled out in view of the constancy in the magnitude of magnetic moment within the range of experimental error (± 0.02) for the complexes obtained from three different preparations. The existence of exchange interactions with very bulky ligands of the type used in the present studies could also be ruled out and, therefore, the intermediate values of magnetic moments observed in the cobalt(II) complexes are possibly due to the equilibrium²⁴⁻²⁶ between the thermally accessible $^4T_{2g}$ and 2E_g states. Magnetic measurements at different temperature would have presented a clear picture of the facts.

Visible spectra of all the complexes contain a strong charge transfer absorption with a shoulder at $\sim 19000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This prevents appearance of any d-d bands.

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